

HUMAN-CENTRIC AI-ENABLED EXTENDED REALITY APPLICATIONS FOR THE
INDUSTRY 5.0 ERA

D5.1 – XR TRAINING MATERIALS, DEMONSTRATORS,
AND PROGRAMS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AMT	Aircraft Maintenance Technician
AR	Augmented Reality
CAMIL	Cognitive Affective Model of Immersive Learning
HMI	Human Machine Interfaces
IHOT	Industrial Internet of Things
LLM	Large Language Models
MR	Mixed Reality
MRTK	Microsoft Mixed Reality Toolkit
SUS	System Usability Scale
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TPAT	Training Programs Authoring Tool
TLX	NASA Task Load Index
UI	User Interface
VR	Virtual Reality
WAIV	Wing Anti-Ice Valve
XR	Extended Reality
XRTP	XR Training Plugin

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable D5.1 XR Training Materials, Demonstrators, and Programs is an output of WP5 for XR-Enabled Operator 5.0 Training. The document reports on the progress and outcomes of two tasks for developing the XR5.0 vision of training in the context of Industry 5.0, namely: T5.1 XR Training Materials and Demonstrators, and T5.4 Training Programs Development. The primary goal of these tasks is to develop the mapping procedure for converting training materials into immersive XR content and provide a system that allows to structure this content into comprehensive training programs tailored for industrial applications.

The deliverable starts by describing the methodology for collecting and analyzing the information on the traditional training materials. This information is detailed at the level of the learning objectives and training contexts in traditional training, its training methods and formats, and the type of training materials. Additionally, the training requirements for operators in traditional training were also analyzed, as well as the suitability for XR. After describing this methodology, the systematic mapping process for the training content to XR-based materials was also detailed on the conversion approach from transforming traditional training resources, such as PDFs, images, and videos, into XR-compatible formats. This process supports a seamless transition from conventional training methods to innovative, immersive digital learning experiences that enhance operator skills and promote efficiency in complex industrial settings.

The vision of each pilot is provided in the following section related to the training materials, as the traditional approach and the XR-based training. Additionally, the report details the development of the XR Training Management System, which comprises two main components: the Training Programs Authoring Tool (TPAT) and the XR Training Plugin (XRTP). TPAT provides a user-friendly web-based interface for managers to create, customize, and organize XR training materials and programs, while XRTP enables operators to access and engage with these programs through XR devices.

The next steps include implementing an automated content extraction tool, launching an initial version of the 3D Model Explorer, connecting the XR Training Plugin with the platform, and establishing an evaluation method for training programs. A complete workflow demonstration of an operator using an XR device to follow a training program is also planned to showcase the system's practical impact.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Deliverable D5.1 XR Training Materials, Demonstrators and Programs is part of the outputs for WP5 focused on XR-Enabled Operator 5.0 Training. The primary aim of this deliverable is to document the activities related to the design and development of the training materials, demonstrators and programs to be used in this project. This deliverable is the first version of the report at M16, that will be complemented by its second version at M30 and documents the progress and results of two key tasks, namely, T5.1 XR Training Materials and Demonstrators and T5.4 Training Programs Development, which form the foundation for developing the XR5.0 operator training.

On one hand, T5.1 focuses on developing and delivering XR-based training materials and demonstrators for the industrial applications covered in XR5.0. The training content will be customized for specific industrial use cases to improve operators' skills in handling complex equipment and processes. The task includes gathering, classifying, and documenting training materials based on job tasks, difficulty levels, and industrial domains. In addition, the task will develop the mapping procedure to map traditional training materials to the XR platform, allowing the display of the training content of the pilots involved in the XR5.0 Training Platform. On the other hand, T5.4 focuses on the development and management of immersive training programs within the XR5.0 Training Platform. This task will provide an XR-based training platform for users to enroll in courses and for stakeholders to upload training materials and demonstrations based on the mapping from Task 5.1. This approach will produce scalable and adaptable training programs for different industrial contexts, supported by the other tasks from WP5, specifically, from the mechanisms developed from T5.3 XR Assets and Devices Orchestration, and integrating with the cloud-based XR training asset repository from T5.2 Cloud Management of XR Training Assets.

This deliverable provides comprehensive documentation of progress in the development and integration of XR-based training materials and programs within the XR5.0 Training Platform. It focuses on the design, classification, and mapping of traditional training materials into immersive XR environments, ensuring a natural transition to innovative training methodologies. Additionally, it details the XR5.0 Training Platform, which enables the creation, customization, and deployment of XR-based training programs. This deliverable builds upon Deliverable D5.3 Training Platform for Operator 5.0, which aims to describe the technical architecture of the XR5.0 Training Platform, its integration mechanisms, core features, and pilot deployment in the XR5.0 project.

The current Deliverable D5.1 will be focused on Task 5.1, which involves the collection and categorization of training materials, as well as Task 5.4, which focuses on structuring immersive training programs for industrial operators. This first version provides a structured foundation for the XR5.0 Training Platform, detailing the design, development, and implementation of training materials and programs.

1.1. Objectives of the Deliverable

The general objective of this deliverable is to report on the integration of traditional training materials and programs into the XR5.0 Training Platform. Thus, ensuring that the transition from conventional methods to XR-based training solutions gathers the main aspects of training by taking advantage of the XR environment characteristics and new features. This document outlines the process of collecting, categorizing, and mapping traditional training content to immersive XR environments, considering industry-specific requirements and constraints focusing also on the methodology to create the XR training programs from the traditional materials.

Another objective is focused on detailing the development of the XR Training Management System, which will provide tools for authoring, managing, and visualizing XR training programs. These tools will allow stakeholders to create, customize, and deploy training content efficiently while maintaining compatibility with existing industrial workflows.

In addition, this deliverable also aims to describe the suitability of XR for different training scenarios, identifying the advantages and limitations of immersive training environments. By leveraging XR technologies, AI-driven interactivity, and cloud-based infrastructure, the deliverable aims to support the development of scalable and adaptable training programs that enhance operator learning and engagement in industrial settings.

This deliverable lays the foundation for the integration of XR-based training into industrial use cases, filling the gap between traditional methods and immersive digital learning experiences. Future iterations will further refine these concepts, ensuring alignment with user needs and technological advancements.

1.2. Structure of the Deliverable

This deliverable is structured in six main sections. Each section of this document focuses on a key aspect to address the objectives of the deliverable related to the process of developing the XR training materials and programs for the XR-Enabled Operator 5.0 Training of XR5.0 project. The organization of the document is depicted below.

The first section is devoted to the introduction of the deliverable, including its objectives (1.1), outlining the motivation and expected contributions, its structure (1.2), and the relation to other deliverables (1.3) to highlight dependencies and complementarities within the XR5.0 framework.

The second section focuses on the traditional training materials and aims to present the data collection procedure (2.1) for gathering conventional training content and categorizes it based on learning objectives (2.2), training contexts (2.2.1), training methods, and formats (2.2.2), and types of training materials (2.2.3). Operators training requirements (2.2.4), while suitability of training materials for XR environments (2.2.5) is also analyzed, ensuring an effective adaptation process.

The third section is related to the mapping procedure between training materials to XR, explores the advantages and limitations of XR environments (3.1) in training scenarios, and introduces the mapping process (3.2) for transitioning traditional materials into XR-based formats. The data collection process is described (3.2.1), along with the methodology (3.2.2) and the description of the mapping strategy and conversion process of training materials to XR-based versions of these materials.

The fourth section aims to describe the training programs by examining both traditional training programs (4.1) and their XR-based counterparts outlining how XR technology enhances training methodologies while maintaining alignment with existing industrial training frameworks.

The fifth section on the XR Training Management System describes this platform and its two core components: the Training Programs Authoring Tool (5.1) and the XR Training Plugin (5.2). Each component is detailed in terms of its description, core features, and functionalities, emphasizing its role in managing and delivering XR-based training programs.

The sixth and final section on Conclusions and Next Steps Towards the Second Version summarizes the key insights of the deliverable and outlines the next steps for further developing and refining the XR training system, ensuring continuous improvement and alignment with industrial training needs.

1.3. Relation to Other Deliverables

For documenting the progress with the development of the procedure for generating the XR training materials and programs as the general objective of this deliverable, this is closely related to other deliverables in the XR5.0 project, particularly D2.2 Reference Architecture Model and Technical Specifications and D5.3 Training Platform for Operator 5.0 v1. These deliverables collectively contribute to the development of a comprehensive, AI-enhanced XR training ecosystem for industrial operators aligned with Industry 5.0 principles.

As regards to D2.2 Reference Architecture Model and Technical Specifications, this deliverable provides the technical foundation for the XR5.0 platform, defining technical specifications, system architecture, APIs, security mechanisms, and interoperability models required for integrating XR-based training solutions.

Deliverable 5.1 builds upon these specifications to ensure that training materials are effectively adapted to XR environments in alignment with the XR5.0 platform’s architectural framework, specifically considering the technical specifications in D2.2 defining the functionalities, APIs, data formats, and internal architecture of XR5.0 components, the enterprise and solution architecture to guide the integration of XR-based training materials and programs with digital twins and AI advanced models for content generation and human-centric interaction.

Deliverable 5.1 relates also with the development process of the XR5.0 Training Platform, as described in D5.3. While D5.3 focuses on the design and implementation of the platform’s infrastructure, D5.1 documents the process of gathering, categorization, and mapping of training materials in XR environments. Specifically, D5.1 contributes to 1) mapping training materials to XR-based content in alignment with the training programs and learning objectives set in D5.3; 2) providing structured training programs that integrate with the TPAT and XRTP described in D5.3; and 3) content deployment through the XR Training Management System and the Hololight Stream and cloud-based XR asset repository for accessing XR training materials and programs through the XR5.0 Training Platform.

This current version of D5.1 ensures that the training contents available in the XR5.0 Training Platform is structured, effective, and aligned with industrial training requirements. The methodologies and frameworks developed in D5.1 will be directly integrated into the platform’s authoring, management, and visualization tools developed under the XR5.0 project.

2. TRADITIONAL TRAINING MATERIALS

This section details the process of collecting and classifying responses from pilot partners regarding the use of traditional training materials. The analysis was conducted in two stages: the first stage focused on the objectives and type of training, while the second stage examined the specific types of materials and content used in traditional training across different use cases. This analysis was performed in general terms and not specifically linked to the pilot's contexts.

This process is part of Task 5.1. The evaluation covers key aspects such as training objectives, delivery methods, material formats, and the potential integration of XR technologies. The primary goal was to assess the context where the training activity takes place or whether a combination of on-the-job and off-the-job training is appropriate. Furthermore, the understanding of the most frequent type of training materials is also of utmost importance as this would guide the development of the training platform and the need for an adaptable XR training platform that can support multiple content formats.

The mapping of traditional training methods and materials is a crucial step for the development of the XR5.0 Training Platform. The insights gained will help ensure that XR technologies are effectively aligned with the current training needs, enhancing workforce learning and operational efficiency. The following sections detail the findings from this process, providing a comprehensive overview of the training materials used in the pilots and their suitability for XR integration.

2.1. Data collection procedure

The data collection process for analyzing training materials involved the systematic distribution and completion of two structured templates by the pilot partners. The first version of the template was shared in May 2024, followed by a second version in July 2024. Pilots were asked to fill in these documents to provide detailed insights into their training methodologies, content, and resources. The objective was to gather comprehensive information about the existing training procedures, facilitating the identification of suitable XR adaptations in the project.

The sample for the analysis of the results on traditional training materials consist of the pilot partners of XR5.0, namely, 6 pilots as follows:

- **Pilot 1** - Rapid Human Centric AI-Enabled Product Design
- **Pilot 2** - Human Centred Remote Maintenance and Asset Management
- **Pilot 3** - Operator 5.0 Training for Smart Water Pipes based on XR Streaming
- **Pilot 4** - Worker Centric Aircraft Maintenance Training
- **Pilot 5** - Increased Effectiveness and Safety of Product Assembly and Repair Processes
- **Pilot 6** - Human Centric Guidance and Troubleshooting for Customer Service

The templates were distributed among these pilot partners to provide information about the training content. The first template was designed to categorize and document the key aspects of training content used in different contexts. It explored the usage context and classified the type of training, covering self-study, instructor-led sessions, in-person training, online courses, blended learning, and other modalities. Furthermore, it documented the formats of training materials, including printed manuals, online courses, videos, interactive simulations, webinars, slide presentations, and hands-on kits. A dedicated content description section allowed for the inclusion of relevant features, session duration, frequency, and the number of sessions. Additional fields captured information about learning objectives, target audiences, language of instruction, and compliance with legal aspects such as copyright, licensing, accreditation, or industry regulations.

The second template consisted of a more detailed procedure for capturing information on the training activities, focusing on four key areas: Details, Logistics, Materials, and Content.

The first section related to training details collected information about the training's usage context, specifically whether it considers on-the-job, off-the-job, or both settings. This section also identified the target audience, learning objectives, prerequisites, and assessment methods used to evaluate training effectiveness.

The second section related to logistics documented the method of training delivery, distinguishing between self-study, instructor-led, or hybrid approaches, but also specified whether the training was conducted in-person, online, or through a blended format while also collecting information about the training location session duration, and available connectivity.

The section related to materials focused on the types of resources used in the training activity, including videos, slides, handouts, online modules, interactive simulations, and hands-on kits, as also the relevance of integrating these materials into the XR platform by ranking their importance for XR adaptation and specifying their formats, such as PDFs, MP4s, or URLs. The last section related to content evaluated the interactivity level of training materials, differentiating between passive observation (expositive) and active participation (practical). It also determined the most suitable XR technologies for each training section, namely VR, AR, or MR would best fit. It also explored adaptive learning features, assessing how training content could be personalized based on individual learner needs, experience levels, or expertise.

2.2. Categorization

The categorization of the results was based on a mixed methods approach considering both quantitative and qualitative analyses for the information provided in the templates. This analysis used different techniques as content analysis, to identify the main topics in specific questions that allowed the participants to elaborate on a given topic, and descriptive statistics based on frequency analysis to determine the frequencies and relative proportions of each category on multiple choice questions. The results were organized into tables and figures with charts for better visualization. This analysis is described in the following sub-sections (2.2.1 to 2.2.5), covering learning objectives, training contexts, training methods and formats, types of training materials, operators training requirements and suitability of training programs to XR.

2.2.1. Learning Objectives and Training Contexts

An evaluation of the learning objectives and training contexts revealed six key themes, each aligned with specific competencies targeted by the training programs: Knowledge acquisition, Operational practice, Maintenance practice, Safety and compliance, Training development, and XR-based learning.

Regarding the first theme related to Knowledge acquisition, several training programs focus on providing essential theoretical knowledge for specific job functions. Participants gain expertise in understanding new devices and codes, product variants, and XR equipment, ensuring they can implement technological updates efficiently in their workplace. Examples of this theme include:

- Learning about new product variants and how to implement them into existing plants.
- Understanding how to develop and deliver VR/AR training sessions tailored to different learner profiles.
- Gaining knowledge about AI-driven training workflows in a VR environment and how to integrate AI into training.

As for Operational practice, a key focus of the training programs is equipping workers with hands-on operational skills needed for machinery and equipment usage. Examples include:

- Learning how to operate HMIs (Human-Machine Interfaces) and handle minor failures.
- Developing expertise in conducting operational tests on machinery.
- Understanding how to follow step-by-step device operation verification instructions to ensure smooth functionality.

For Maintenance practice, some training programs focus on routine maintenance and troubleshooting, ensuring workers can identify, diagnose, and repair technical issues. These objectives include:

- Conducting regular machinery maintenance checks to ensure safe and efficient operation.
- Learning to retrofit and update older laboratory instruments to meet modern standards.
- Developing skills to identify and resolve machinery issues proactively.

As regards to Safety and compliance, this theme was also chosen as being important for training programs. The examples include the following descriptions:

- Training employees to use personal protective equipment.
- Learning to remove defective components and install replacements according to safety guidelines.

Regarding training development, some training programs focus on developing the ability of employees to train others. These objectives include:

- Developing skills to deliver training sessions and create effective training materials.
- Manage and update online learning platforms.
- Learning to customize training workflows to match individual skill levels.

As for XR-based learning, specific training programs already focus on immersive learning experiences using XR technologies. These objectives include:

- Using XR technology to receive real-time feedback during assembly tasks to improve techniques.
- Learning how to use AR for identifying and repairing defects in edge devices.
- Understanding XR technology for adaptive training for tailored learning experiences.

The analysis of learning objectives in traditional training programs reveals that some programs focus on knowledge acquisition, while others focus on hands-on experience, troubleshooting, and compliance with safety standards.

Specifically regarding the Training Context, the options were related to 1) On-the-Job Training, for training that occurs while the employee is performing the actual job tasks during their regular work schedule; 2) Off-the-Job Training, for training that takes place outside of the actual job environment, often in a classroom or training facility; or 3) Both contexts of training in on-the-job and off-the-job training.

According to the provided information, the analysis reveals a strong emphasis on On-the-Job Training (45%), suggesting that a significant portion of training is conducted while employees perform their actual job tasks, ensuring hands-on learning and immediate application of skills in real world scenarios. This may be particularly beneficial in technical and operational roles, where real-time problem-solving and practical skill development are essential. In addition, there was also a substantial proportion of responses that involve both types of training in both On-the-Job and Off-the-Job training settings (41%). This dual applicability suggests a hybrid learning approach, where foundational knowledge can be acquired in Off-the-Job settings and later applied in real-world scenarios. A smaller proportion was evidenced for Off-the-Job Training, suggesting that while some training is conducted in classrooms or training facilities, it is not the dominant method (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Most frequent usage context of the traditional training programs

2.2.2. Training Methods and Formats

The analysis of the training methods used in the programs was conceptualized in three different categories, namely, Self-study when training is completed individually; Instructor-led for training conducted by an instructor, either in-person or virtually; and Both for training that considers both methods.

For Self-study methods, a significant proportion of the training programs rely on self-study, either independently or supported by a virtual coach (avatar). This method allows trainees to progress at their own pace, making it ideal for acquiring theoretical knowledge and operational procedures. The inclusion of avatars suggests an emphasis on adaptive learning, where AI-driven avatars may provide guidance, feedback, and real-time assistance to simulate an instructor's role.

Instructor-led training was chosen in a smaller proportion of the use cases as the sole method. These results indicate that while guided learning is relevant, most programs prioritize flexibility through self-paced or blended learning approaches. Instructor-led training is used, for instance, to replace the Wing Anti-Ice Valve (WAIV) for the aircraft maintenance pilot where complex hands-on tasks are prioritized.

As for the combination of self-study and instructor-led training, the same proportion of training programs along with self-study solely, follow this blended approach. This hybrid method provides structured guidance from an instructor while allowing learners to reinforce concepts through self-paced study. Such a model is particularly well suited for technical training, where foundational knowledge can be acquired independently and later applied in practical, instructor-led sessions.

These results demonstrate diverse approaches to training, integrating both self-study and instructor-led training to attend to different learning needs. The distribution of methods indicates a preference for flexible and adaptive learning formats, leveraging both independent study and guided instruction (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Most frequently used training methods

As regards to the analysis of training delivery formats, this topic was analyzed considering three types of delivery formats, specifically, In-person, Online, and Both formats.

Regarding in-person Training, a significant proportion of training programs are delivered solely in person, focusing on hands-on tasks, equipment handling, and practical demonstrations.

As for online training a slightly smaller proportion of training is conducted exclusively online, being based on digital platforms, e-learning modules, and virtual environments. Online training is ideal for theoretical learning, software-based skills, and interactive simulations, allowing learners to complete training at their own pace and from any location.

The combination of in-person and online training was the most chosen option, revealing that most partners follow a hybrid delivery model for training delivery, combining in-person sessions with online learning. This approach offers the advantages of both formats, allowing trainees to acquire foundational knowledge online and later apply it in practical, supervised settings.

In sum, this analysis highlights a strong focus on digital learning solutions while still recognizing the importance of in-person, hands-on experiences for skill-based training (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Most frequently used training delivery format

2.2.3. Types of Training Materials

This analysis was conducted to understand the most common types of materials used in traditional training. This procedure was important to identify the most common material types to be used by the XR5.0 Training Platform. In addition, this phase was the foundation of the training platform's main features and the respective mapping procedure between the training content and the XR training materials to be used in this platform. The collection of this information required the specification of the content formats of each resource, for instance, in PDF, MP4, URL, and other types of materials.

The analysis of traditional training materials reveals a diverse range of content formats, emphasizing the need for flexibility in training delivery.

The materials include documents, videos, online resources, and interactive content, ensuring comprehensive coverage of training topics, as described below.

Document-based training in PDF format, are the most widely used type of materials used for traditional training. This includes instructional manuals and standard operating procedures. Other types of documents reported are PPT files that include presentation slides for structured lessons, also handouts, and text-based reference materials. The prevalence of using PDFs highlights the need for structured, text-based learning.

Video-based training is also very relevant for traditional training. The use of MP4 videos reveals the importance of visual demonstrations, tutorials, and recorded lectures. Videos are particularly effective for explaining complex concepts using animations and demonstrations.

Web-based training using URLs was also used as training content for interactive learning materials that included online modules and e-learning platforms, and interactive simulations. JSON files were also mentioned under this category.

In-person (physical) training was also reported in some instances, which may involve hands-on skills and practical exercises. This analysis underscores the need for XR integration that can support PDFs, document viewing, interactive content, and videos, ensuring a smooth transition from traditional to extended reality-based training. These training materials' proportions are represented in the following figure (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Most common formats of traditional materials

The following table depicts the primary material type for each format of the training assets used in the traditional training (Table 1). The classification of training materials by format highlights the distribution of content types across different media. The data shows a clear preference for structured documents and interactive digital resources, reinforcing the importance of text-based materials, video content, and web-based learning modules.

PDFs represent the most frequently used format, with materials categorized as:

- Documents (51%), consisting mainly of manuals, reports, and reference guides that provide structured, text-based training.
- Presentations (41%), used for instructor-led training or self-guided learning, typically containing slides and key points.
- Other (8%), include miscellaneous content types such as checklists, procedural documents, and supplementary reference materials.

Videos are widely used for demonstrations and hands-on learning, being categorized as:

- Tutorials (21%), including step-by-step instructional videos providing guided learning experiences.
- Demonstrations (7%), describing real-world applications and procedures.
- Lectures (3%), used for recorded presentations covering theoretical knowledge.
- Unspecified (69%), including other types of videos that do not have a clearly defined category.

Web-based training materials describe the use of digital and interactive learning experiences, categorized as:

- Online Modules (63%), including digital learning content, e-learning courses, interactive lessons, and structured online training programs.
- Interactive Simulations (34%), that describe hands-on virtual experiences.
- Webinars (3%), that consist of live or recorded sessions for remote learning.

Table 1. Material type for most common formats

Format	Material type
PDF	Document (51%) Presentation (41%) Other (8%)
MP4	Tutorial (21%) Demonstration (7%) Lecture (3%) Unspecified (69%)

URL	Online module (63%) Interactive simulation (34%) Webinar (3%)
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The most reported PDF files were documents. The analysis of document types within PDF training materials reveals a strong reliance on structured instructional content, with manuals being the most common format, representing 55% of the total. Manuals serve as detailed instructional guides, providing comprehensive explanations of procedures, equipment usage, and standardized workflows. Guides (14%) and protocols (9%) complement manuals by offering quick-start references, best practices, and compliance guidelines, ensuring adherence to industry standards. Handouts (5%) are less frequent and likely used for summaries, checklists, or quick-reference materials. Additionally, 17% of the documents remain unspecified, indicating the need for better categorization or representing diverse, uncategorized training materials. The predominance of manuals and structured documents suggests that training programs prioritize detailed instructional content to ensure effective knowledge transfer and operational consistency (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Reported types of documents in each pilot context

The most common type in URL format were online modules for traditional training. The online modules were analyzed further to depict the distribution of different types of online modules within URL-based resources. The data highlights that Practical Exercises (33%) are the largest portion, indicating a strong focus on hands-on, applied learning through digital platforms. Unspecified modules (33%) account for an equally significant part, suggesting that a considerable proportion of online training materials have not been categorized or consist of diverse contents. Quizzes (17%) are used as an assessment tool. Similarly, AR/VR-based modules (17%) highlight the integration of immersive technologies in training, providing interactive and simulation-based learning experiences. The overall distribution suggests that online training modules are designed to be interactive and engaging, with a strong emphasis on practical application and immersive learning experiences (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Most frequent type of online modules used in the traditional training programs

The analysis of training materials in Table 2 shows that PDFs (35%), MP4 videos (25%), and URLs (16%) are the main formats used, highlighting the need for the XR platform to support documents, videos and interactive materials. Manuals (55%) and presentations (41%) are the main types of PDF materials, suggesting that these should be adapted into interactive XR formats for effective learning.

Videos, mainly tutorials (21%) and demonstrations (7%), are underutilized, with many remaining uncategorized (69%). Online modules (63%) and interactive simulations (34%) form URL-based content, with practical exercises and quizzes being key components. Overall, adapting manuals, presentations, and videos into immersive, structured formats will be essential for optimizing XR-based learning experiences. The following table depicts the main conclusions from the analysis of the training materials and formats.

Table 2. Main outcomes about the traditional training materials

Finding	Takeaway
PDF (35%) is the most common format, followed by MP4 (25%) and URLs (16%).	The training platform should support documents (PDF), videos (MP4), and interactive materials (URL).
Documents (51%) and Presentations (41%) were the most common type of PDFs. As for Document type, Manuals (55%) are the most common, followed by Guides (14%), Protocols (9%) and Handouts (5%).	XR training should focus on XR-based versions of manuals and presentations using the same adaptation methods for the other document types.
Only three types of Videos were identified: Tutorials (21%), Demonstrations (7%) and Lectures (3%). Most were not specified (69%).	XR training should support XR video playback inside the XR environment.
Online Modules (63%) and Interactive Simulations (34%) were the most common URL types. As for Online Modules, Practical Exercises (33%) are the	Given the variability of URL content and the suitability for XR environments, another relevant

<p>most common followed by quizzes and AR/VR apps.</p>	<p>feature may be that the platform defers web content to each device’s native browser.</p> <p>Exploring an authoring tool to create workflows and quizzes within the platform can be a valuable option.</p>
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2.2.4. Operators training requirements

The identification of operators’ training requirements, considering expertise and experience levels across different industrial contexts, was evaluated by the questions related to the Target Audience, Prerequisites, and the Adaptive learning features of the training. As regards to the Target Audience, the results show mainly four categories (New employees, Existing staff, Experienced staff, and Specialized roles). The results show that Experienced and Existing staff are the target audience of training programs (Figure 7).

Figure 7 - Target audience

On Prerequisites, the responses were distributed among the following categories (Technical proficiency, Basic operational knowledge, Specialized training, Digital literacy, XR familiarity, language and communication skills, field-specific experience), where the most reported was Basic operational knowledge (Figure 8). The results show that acquiring Basic operational knowledge was the most selected category.

Figure 8 - Traditional training prerequisites

On the third dimension related to adaptive learning features, the most chosen option was Task performance and Knowledge level among Experience levels (Figure 9).

Figure 9 - Adaptive learning features reported by each pilot partner

2.2.5. Suitability for XR

The analysis of XR suitability highlights user preferences for integrating VR, AR, and MR into training programs. The use of VR may be more suited for standalone experiences where users are fully immersed in virtual content, whereas AR may be ideal for on-the-job activities where virtual content provides support during operations and MR for scenarios requiring a blend of virtual and real-world elements. Suitable for tasks involving immersive experiences coupled with real-time interaction with the physical environment.

The results from the pilot participants revealed a strong preference for MR, followed by AR and VR, depending on the specific training requirements and user needs. Table 3 describes the main features of each XR technique.

Table 3. Features associated with each XR technique

Aspect	Mixed Reality (MR)	Augmented Reality (AR)	Virtual Reality (VR)
User preference	Most preferred option overall	Strong preference, especially for on-the-job training	Second most preferred option
Training type suitability	Ideal for practical, hands-on training with active participation	Best for expositive training with passive participation	Suitable for both expositive and practical training, especially in simulated contexts
Environment interaction	Real-time interaction with physical environment with digital overlays	Augmented instructions in real-world setting	Full virtual immersion with no real-world interaction
Best use cases	Industrial training, equipment handling, interactive simulations	Maintenance, troubleshooting, procedural guidance	Complex procedural training, high-risk environments
Level of immersion	Blended immersion, integrating real and virtual worlds	Low to moderate immersion	High immersion
Hardware/setup requirements	Requires advanced MR devices; more complex setup	Lighter hardware (e.g., AR glasses or tablets)	Requires dedicated VR headsets and spatial setup
Limitations	Less immersive than VR in fully simulated contexts	Not suitable for fully immersive training.	Cybersickness

- This analysis suggests that training adaptation should prioritize MR/AR for interactive tasks or real-world assistance, and VR for full-immersion learning, ensuring that XR technology is optimally aligned with training needs. The results from pilots’ preferences are depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Suitability for extended reality reported by technique

3. MAPPING TRADITIONAL TRAINING MATERIALS TO XR

This section aims to describe the mapping process of converting training materials to XR-based materials. The mapping process involves both semi-automated and automated methods to extract key training elements from traditional materials to convert them into dynamic and immersive formats suitable for XR platforms. Managers can create XR learning experiences that enhance skill transfer and retention to be provided to trainees in an immersive training setting. This integration not only facilitates “learning by doing” in controlled virtual settings but also supports on-the-job training through augmented overlays that provide real-time guidance during operational tasks.

3.1. Advantages and limitations of XR environments

The recent advancements in XR technology have been contributing to providing more natural user experiences blending real and virtual elements [1]. XR is increasingly being explored as a transformative solution for training in industrial contexts [2]. In alignment with the human-centric principles of Industry 5.0, XR training environments enable immersive, adaptive, and more organic interaction with the training contents, potentially improving the efficiency and effectiveness of complex procedural training in different industry scenarios [3]. On one hand, the simulation of realistic scenarios without the logistical constraints or risks associated with real-world operations offers a scalable and engaging solution for knowledge improvement and skill acquisition in off-the-job contexts. On the other hand, the overlay of information onto real-world environments is equally valuable for refining skills during operational tasks in on-the-job settings [4].

One of the most important advantages of XR is its capacity to deliver immersive and experience-based learning [5]. Instead of passively viewing information through text or videos, operators can interact with 3D environments that replicate the tasks and tools used in real settings. This “learning by doing” [6] approach improves memory retention and skill transfer, making XR especially effective for technical and manual procedures. XR training platforms can support both off-the-job and on-the-job training, enabling hybrid learning models [7]. For instance, theoretical knowledge can be acquired in a VR environment where the operator can first perform the procedure in VR in off-the-job settings, gaining confidence and familiarity with the tools and sequence [8]. Later, the same technician can use MR in the field to practice the learned skills while receiving guidance in the procedure in the real environment for enhanced transfer of the technical skills.

Existing training methods fail to consider individual differences in learning styles, cognitive load, or engagement. XR environments can overcome this by incorporating personalization features that tailor the training experience to individuals. Using implicit data such as eye movements, facial expressions, and performance measures like execution time and hits/errors in task execution, training platforms can detect stress and cognitive overload and adapt accordingly. This adaptability is supported by cognitive learning models such as the Cognitive Affective Model of Immersive Learning - CAMIL model [9], which accounts for cognitive (e.g., working memory, information processing), affective (e.g., motivation, emotions), and motivational (e.g., expectations and learner’s goals) dimensions on learning experiences. Based on these factors, XR training platforms can adjust the content to better suit the user’s needs. Another advantage is the possibility of having real-time feedback and AI integration [10]. For example, XR environments can be enhanced with AI-driven features such as voice assistants and visual recognition tools. These features provide real-time feedback during training, contributing to correct errors and reinforce learning with training. Cloud-based XR platforms, such as the XR5.0 Training Platform [7], allow organizations to centrally manage training resources and applications. XR content can be updated remotely, displayed on various XR devices, and adapted for different user profiles or job roles. This allows companies to scale training efforts across multiple locations without the need for expensive physical setups or dedicated instructors.

However, there are also several challenges that need to be addressed for the effective deployment of the XR environment for training. One of the primary challenges of XR environments is their reliance on advanced hardware and software. Cloud-based training platforms face another challenge that is related to the required bandwidth and stable internet connections to stream high-fidelity 3D environments in real time.

In some industrial settings, especially in remote or bandwidth-limited environments, this technical infrastructure may be lacking or cost-prohibitive [11]. Another challenge is related to the user interface (UI) in XR. The user interface progressed from the traditional Windows interface to advanced interfaces in XR that mimic human behavioral actions [12]. For users not familiar with immersive technologies, XR systems may present additional challenges. Designing XR environments with intuitive user interfaces is critical to overcoming this limitation. UI design evaluation is typically conducted for user-friendliness that relates to visualization and interaction [13]. These dimensions are often assessed through usability testing, which may involve specific tools such as the System Usability Scale (SUS), NASA Task Load Index (TLX) or broader frameworks like the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [14].

XR environments represent a significant advancement in training methodology, particularly for industrial applications aligned with Industry 5.0. Their ability to deliver immersive, personalized, and data-driven training enables more effective learning experiences, better knowledge retention, and greater worker readiness. By integrating cognitive models like CAMIL and using implicit metrics for real-time adaptation, XR platforms can tailor training to individual needs.

3.2. Mapping Process and XR-based Training Material Types

The mapping process of training materials to immersive XR-based content for the XR5.0 Training Platform derived from a multistage process involving inputs from the different partners in WP5 and the Pilots in WP6. This approach is essential for enabling more engaging, adaptive, and human-centric training aligned with Industry 5.0 principles. The various stages of the mapping process of traditional material to XR materials are described according to the following sub-subsections.

3.2.1. Data Collection

The mapping process began with the data collection procedure about the training materials used in each of the pilot's contexts. The procedure for collecting this information was based on a questionnaire as described above that was designed specifically for gathering information about the training materials and programs. This questionnaire aimed to collect detailed information on the types and formats of training materials currently in use. As described above in the section dedicated to the analysis of the traditional training content, the result from this methodology allows us to identify that PDF documents, videos, and URLs were the most frequently used and training-relevant materials across pilots (Figure 11). These were prioritized for conversion into XR formats due to their instructional value and adaptability. Regarding URLs, as the content may be of different types, the platform will either not support such content type or defer to the device native browser. Nevertheless, as the project progresses, this topic will be further discussed, given the importance of such materials to the XR5.0 Pilots.

Figure 11 - Main types of traditional training material

3.2.2. Methodology

The methodology was shaped through a combination of synchronous meetings held within the dedicated XR5.0 work package and ongoing asynchronous communication. The mapping process was developed using co-creation and participatory design approaches to define how training content could be converted into XR-based content for use on the training platform. This process involved close coordination between pilot leaders, developers, and training experts to ensure that the final XR content would address real needs on the ground.

The mapping strategy defines a systematic procedure for transforming conventional training materials, such as PDFs, images and videos, into immersive and interactive XR-based training content. This strategy is central to the XR5.0 Training Platform’s mission to modernize industrial training by enabling scalable, adaptable, and personalized learning experiences. Figure 12 illustrates this process.

Figure 12 - Illustration of the mapping strategy

The process starts with the upload of training materials into the XR5.0 platform via the web-based admin interface that is described in Section 5. Each file is stored in the XR Asset Repository, which serves as a secure and central storage system for all training content.

For instance, consider a PDF document detailing the operational procedure for maintaining a machine component. This file, once uploaded to the platform, is linked to a corresponding asset entry that manages its availability, versioning, and associations within the training program. From this point, the platform supports several conversion workflows, depending on the intended XR material.

3.2.3. Mapping Strategy and Conversion Processes

Based on the evaluation of traditional materials and pilot needs, seven core XR Training Material formats were defined (Table 4).

Table 4. Description of XR-Training Materials

XR Training Materials	Description
Checklists	List of items to support operators during tasks.
Enhanced Videos	Videos with chapters and annotated timestamps.
Interactive Images	Images with annotated areas that redirect to other contents.
Workflows	Step-by-step sequential instructions to guide operators.
XR-AI Assistant	AI voice assistants to support operators within the XR environment with knowledge about the procedure.
3D Model Explorer	3D models exploded views with parts identification.
3D Workflows	Step-by-step sequential instructions guiding operators, using a 3D model as a reference to highlight and animate parts.

The previously defined XR-based materials are created from traditional training materials. Each content type was linked to one or more XR outputs through a clearly defined pipeline:

PDF to Checklist or Workflow

Using semi-automated the user can upload a PDF file to the TPAT (described in further details in section 5) and extract the text and image content of the PDF. The user can choose whether the elements are structured into checklists or step-by-step workflows, which the trainees can follow inside the XR environment. For example, a checklist may allow the user to check the different steps in the disassembly of a component, whereas the workflows provide step-by-step sequential instructions to guide operators on a given procedure. The partners in WP5 are coordinating with partners from INNOV to develop a solution based on LLM to extract procedural steps and convert these steps into structured formats automatically to provide an alternative to the semi-automated method that is being implemented.

PDF or Image to Interactive Images

For contents including diagrams, technical illustrations or labeled parts, these materials can be converted into interactive images annotated using a visual editor within the platform, allowing the creation of clickable zones that trigger tooltips with text content and links to other related materials.

Videos to Enhanced Videos

Training videos (MP4) can be augmented with chapter markers and annotations to form enhanced videos with clickable timestamped notes that improve navigation and annotations for accessing extra information or other related materials.

3D Model to 3D Model Explorer

Uploaded 3D models (e.g., in FBX format) are processed by a 3D model importer integrated into the platform. This tool automatically generates exploded views and part identification labels.

3D Model to 3D Workflow

A solution currently being under analysis is the use of 3D models to be linked to interactive workflows, allowing users to see animated sequences within the model, helping visualize and reinforce the correct procedure.

XR-AI Assistant

Documents containing procedural knowledge or FAQs can also be parsed and indexed by an AI assistant based on LLMs. This assistant is integrated into the XR environment and allows trainees to ask questions during the training process. This solution is still under development for the training platform.

The following table describes this mapping procedure between traditional materials and the XR-based materials to be used in the XR5.0 Training Platform (Table 5).

Table 5. Description of conversion/adaptation process for XR materials

Input	Conversion / Adaptation Process	XR Materials
PDFs	Semi-automated extraction Automated generation (LLMs)	Checklists
PDFs	Semi-automated extraction Automated generation (LLMs)	Workflows

PDFs	Semi-automated extraction Automated generation (LLMs)	Interactive Images
PDFs	Automated generation	XR-AI Assistant
Images	Annotation	Interactive Images
Videos	Annotation	Enhanced Videos
3D Models	Automated generation	3D Model Explorer
3D Models	Manual configuration	3D Workflows

These processes are being implemented in the web-based training authoring tool, being further rendered in the XR Training Plugin, which will be described under section 5 of this deliverable.

3.2.4. Challenges of the Mapping Procedure

Some challenges arise when converting information from traditional training used in the pilots’ contexts to the training platform. Issues such as the preservation of content accuracy while ensuring compatibility across diverse XR devices is critical for effective training. One key issue is related to the heterogeneity of traditional materials that demands for flexible mapping strategies that can be tailored to various industrial contexts and learning goals. In addition, it is crucial to ensure that XR-based training is engaging for operators, while also maintaining high levels of usability and ease of interaction within XR environments. These challenges will be addressed during the experimental stages of the use cases, which will evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed XR5.0 Training Platform solutions.

4. TRAINING PROGRAMS

Traditional training programs in industrial contexts rely on conventional materials such as printed manuals, technical data sheets, videos, and in-person sessions to impart essential skills. These methods, while proven, face several challenges. For instance, new product variants often require installation procedures that deviate from existing documentation. Moreover, on-the-job training can disrupt production schedules and incur additional costs, especially when experienced technicians are not readily available to provide guidance.

To overcome some of these limitations, the XR5.0 Training Platform has been developed to transform traditional training content into immersive, interactive experiences. By converting static resources into dynamic XR-based materials, the platform enables training that is both engaging and effective. Interactive elements such as 3D model visualizations, checklists, and workflows enhance understanding and facilitate step-by-step guidance, thereby improving skill transfer and retention.

Two important features of the training platform are content personalization and adaptation to user profiles, with the aim of delivering tailored learning experiences. These features are currently being developed under WP3, which focuses on Human-Centric Digital Twins and XR Personalization. Once integrated into the training platform, these modules will deliver personalized and adaptive training content to each user. For example, managers will be able to categorize training programs and materials to customize them for individual profiles. This ensures that specific programs and materials are accessible only to the appropriate users, in line with personalization goals. In addition to static categorization, content visualization will dynamically adapt to each user, based on their behavior—captured through implicit metrics such as non-verbal responses or task performance. Considering both the user profile and behavioral data, the interface will adjust in real time to enhance efficiency and usability.

For allowing such features, a flexible, many-to-many structure is crucial for creating scalable, modular, and personalized training programs in the XR5.0 Training Platform. The following diagram demonstrates the structure of the training programs in the XR training system. It highlights the relationships between Programs and XR Training Materials, emphasizing a many-to-many (N: N) connection between elements. According to this structure, a program can include many XR Training Materials, and each XR Training Material can be linked to many Programs (many-to-many relationship). In addition, an XR Training Material can reference multiple other XR Training Materials, creating a self-referencing many-to-many relationship representing training dependencies, sequences, and modular structures of training programs to be used in the XR5.0 Training Platform. This structure also allows linking training materials to other training materials depicting relevant information for a given learning goal (Figure 13).

Figure 13 - Structure of the training programs in the XR training system

The next topics aim to describe the traditional training approaches that are employed in each of the pilots while linking to the advantages of XR-based training and the features of the XR5.0 Training Platform.

4.1. Traditional Training Programs to XR-based Training Programs

To demonstrate the flexibility, scalability, and real-world applicability of the XR5.0 Training Platform, six pilots have been established across diverse industrial domains. Each pilot describes the traditional training methods and challenges associated with this type of training. These challenges are addressed by integrating XR tools in a training platform. These pilots showcase how XR5.0 can transform training into a more immersive, adaptive, and efficient process but also illustrate its potential to enhance human-machine collaboration in alignment with the principles of Industry 5.0.

4.1.1. Pilot 1 - Rapid Human Centric AI-Enabled Product Design

Traditional Training

When an assembly line is being set up, technicians use manuals and data sheets and get help from experienced colleagues to carry out their tasks. Training sessions are held both on-the-job and off-the-job to ensure efficiency in the training of various tasks. Nonetheless, conventional training methods present several difficulties, including:

- New products or product variants that need to be installed differently than those explained in traditional training material.
- Training on the job impacts project schedules and increases costs.
- Experienced technicians may not be available on-site or have the time for on-the-job training.

XR-based Training

The XR5.0 Training Platform will improve commissioning training with AI-generated training instructions based on traditional training material (office files, manuals, data sheets) making static content interactive (under development), and the 3D models for an immersive experience. Exploded views of 3D models in an XR environment improves understanding the setup of e.g. the training for a robotic cell. XR streaming allows an end-device agnostic solution that can be used in various situations and adapted to the needs of the technician.

4.1.2. Pilot 2 - Human Centred Remote Maintenance and Asset Management

Traditional Training

Training for the maintenance and calibration of SH's laboratory instruments—such as polarimeters, refractometers, and analyzers—is traditionally conducted through a mix of printed manuals, technical data sheets, and in-person training sessions. Technicians often rely on internal documentation or direct support from senior experts to understand complex procedures. While this has been effective to a degree, several challenges persist:

- Many instruments are customized or adapted to specific industrial environments, making general training materials insufficiently precise.
- Maintenance often requires quick adaptation to unfamiliar models or configurations, not fully covered in existing manuals.
- On-the-job training is limited by expert availability and becomes costly due to the need for travel or extended downtime.
- The increasing complexity of instrumentation and diagnostics demands a deeper level of contextual understanding than static documents can provide.
- Frequent software updates and hardware revisions can render older training materials outdated, making it difficult for technicians to rely on past documentation for current procedures.

These limitations underscore the need for a more adaptive, personalized, and accessible training approach—one that XR5.0 aims to fulfill by integrating AI-supported visual guidance and remote collaboration directly into the technician’s workflow.

XR-based Training

The XR5.0 Training Platform transforms traditional maintenance training by turning static content—such as equipment manuals, service protocols, and troubleshooting guides—into immersive, interactive training modules. Technicians can now engage with 3D models of SH’s laboratory instruments through step-by-step procedures visualized directly in the XR environment. These modules support both remote and on-the-job training, enabling technicians to practice complex calibration and retrofitting tasks in a safe, simulated setting. Integrated AI capabilities enhance the training by offering real-time guidance and contextual explanations based on the technician’s interaction and performance.

4.1.3. Pilot 3 - Operator 5.0 Training for Smart Water Pipes based on XR Streaming ***Traditional Training***

In the pipe rehabilitation and maintenance industry, traditional training for equipment maintenance and pipe maintenance operators includes a structured approach combining theoretical learning, practical exercises, and multimedia resources.

The operator training traditionally includes:

- Classroom-based Instruction: Workers study training manuals, industry guidelines, and safety protocols related to pipeline rehabilitation.
- Instructional Videos & Digital Resources: Training sessions incorporate videos and digital guides to visually demonstrate repair techniques, leak detection methods, and equipment operation.
- Hands-on Workshops: Practical sessions allow trainees to gain experience in pipe inspection, damage assessment, and rehabilitation using conventional tools and materials.
- Field Training & Supervised Practice: Workers participate in real-world maintenance projects under expert supervision to apply their learning in actual work environments.
- Safety and Compliance Training: Focuses on industry safety standards, environmental regulations, and emergency response procedures to ensure safe working conditions.
- Equipment Handling & Maintenance: Trainees learn to operate, troubleshoot, and maintain traditional tools and machinery used in pipeline rehabilitation.

By integrating theoretical knowledge with practical application, this training approach ensures that workers are well-equipped to handle pipeline maintenance and rehabilitation tasks efficiently and safely.

XR-based Training

The XR5.0 Training Platform plays a pivotal role in transforming traditional training content into XR-based learning experiences. The XR Training Management System within the platform converts static materials such as images, videos, and PDFs (manuals) into interactive, XR-ready formats, providing an immersive training experience. Uploaded content is digitized and transformed, making images, PDFs, videos, 3D models, and 2D drawings accessible during AR-based training sessions.

The XR-based training system for smart water pipe rehabilitation integrates Augmented Reality (AR), real-time sensor data, and AI-driven support to offer a hands-on, interactive learning environment. Operators using AR smart glasses can view live sensor data overlaid on virtual models of physical pipes, allowing them to identify issues like leaks or pressure drops. AI models support video anomaly detection, and these would be displayed on the virtual pipe at the anomaly location, and an AI chatbot offers instant, step-by-step repair and maintenance guidance by querying digital manuals. The training program incorporates 3D models, PDFs, and instructional videos, helping workers follow AR-projected repair procedures while interacting

with various digital resources. This immersive training method enhances skill development, reduces training time, and fosters efficient problem-solving for pipeline maintenance tasks.

4.1.4. Pilot 4 - Worker Centric Aircraft Maintenance Training

Traditional Training

In aircraft maintenance training, technicians typically rely on digital manuals and videos, instruction, and hands-on practice to learn the procedures for maintaining and repairing critical aircraft components such as the Wing Anti-Ice Valve (WAIV). Training sessions may be conducted both in on-the-job and off-the-job contexts to learn how to disassemble and repair in controlled environments before applying these skills in real-world scenarios. However, traditional training presents several challenges, including:

- Limited real-world simulation, in which technicians may not get frequent hands-on experience with critical components in realistic failure scenarios.
- High operational downtime: Training on physical aircraft parts may impact maintenance schedules and increase costs.
- Lack of personalized guidance: Training methods may be standardized, not adapting to individual technicians' skill levels and profiles.

XR-based Training

The XR5.0 Training Platform enhances traditional aircraft maintenance training by introducing immersive, efficient, and personalized learning methods. With XR streaming, high-fidelity XR experiences are not dependent on processing capacity of the devices, enabling flexible and scalable deployment across different locations.

The conversion of training materials (PDFs, videos, manuals) into XR-compatible formats transforms passive content into interactive and engaging training programs. XR-based visualization allows AMT technicians to explore and conduct exploded views of 3D models such as those involving the WAIV device in on-the-job settings. Personalized and adaptive content adjusts training to individual skill levels and behavior, ensuring that each technician receives the right level of challenge and support for a tailored experience that enhances retention.

4.1.5. Pilot 5 - Increased Effectiveness and Safety of Product Assembly and Repair Processes

Traditional Training

Currently, training for the assembly and repair process of the GUARDIAN IIOT devices for surveillance rule-based incident response happens via documents describing assembly processes, manuals of the different parts, troubleshooting guides, and hands-on training. One of the main challenges during this process is that it requires both physical (like properly wiring components) and cognitive tasks, like configuring and troubleshooting networking.

Another limitation is represented by the difficulty to recreate real-world complexity in the training classroom, and often, training requires experienced technicians/managers to spend significant amounts of time guiding the less experienced technicians.

XR-based Training

XR training is very well suited for training in tasks like IIOT device assembly due to the ability to create digital twins of these devices relatively easily and use them in simulations of real-world scenarios that would be hard to otherwise replicate in a classroom or laboratory setting.

The traditional materials for the training (manuals, videos, documents) are all handled by the XR5.0 Training Platform, and they will be used to provide personalized training to technicians in a realistic environment and recommendations for on-the-job tasks. The most relevant of the XR-compatible formats are the Checklists and Workflows that will be used to create training exercises with steps the technician will have to successfully complete.

4.1.6. Pilot 6 - Human Centric Guidance and Troubleshooting for Customer Service

Traditional Training

In traditional training at LNS, new employees are primarily trained in equipment maintenance and troubleshooting. The training follows a structured progression, from beginner to expert level, incorporating active learning methods that allow technicians to gradually acquire the necessary skills to diagnose and resolve failures. These sessions combine digital manuals, instructional videos, guided instruction, and hands-on exercises to ensure a comprehensive understanding of procedures. Training can take place both in real-world contexts and controlled environments before being applied in the field.

Additionally, new training programs are needed to be created without requiring advanced IT expertise. For example, the technical documentation team should be trained to create and update digital manuals, and teams should have access to tools that allow them to design immersive learning experiences (XR training).

XR-based Training

At LNS, we first establish a clear distinction between beginner and expert levels. A beginner has limited experience and requires foundational training and more guidance, while an expert has extensive hands-on experience, can independently diagnose and resolve complex issues, and is capable of mentoring others.

To create new training programs, we start by identifying the training needs based on operational requirements and skill gaps. The process begins with using existing resources, such as technical documentation produced by the technical documentation team, along with other internal sources. These materials form the foundation for developing structured training content. Training can help understanding procedures based on images, 3D plans, or diagrams. This ensures that the training is both practical and effective for technicians at all levels.

It is important to be able to calculate the time required to complete a training or a specific step within the training. Additionally, there should be a system in place to track progress, such as a grading system, to confirm that the session has been successfully completed.

5. XR TRAINING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The XR Training Management System provides an integrated workflow for creating, managing, and accessing immersive training materials. This system can be used by a manager who creates new training programs using the TPAT to develop or update XR training programs and materials. These resources are then rendered in the XRTP. The operators can access the XR training content through this tool, which delivers an immersive learning experience in real-time on the XR devices. Refer to D5.3 Training Platform for Operator 5.0 V1 for the technical description of the XR Training Management System.

The distinction between the TPAT from the XRTP ensures that managers can easily manage and update the training programs, integrate new content, and track performance across multiple training scenarios, while operators have a straightforward way to engage with the XR-based training materials. This architecture promotes the scalability of this solution and flexibility across different industry scenarios.

5.1. Training Programs Authoring Tool (TPAT)

The TPAT is a web-based system that allows managers to create, modify, and monitor XR training materials and programs. It is specifically designed to adapt traditional training content, such as PDFs, images, and videos, to immersive formats suitable to be used in XR environments. The following diagram illustrates the interaction between the modules of the TPAT (Figure 14).

Figure 14 - Diagram illustrating the interaction between modules of the TPAT

Core Features and Functionalities

At a functional level, the TPAT is divided into interconnected modules, each contributing to a specific role in the content creation and management workflow, as depicted in Table 6.

Table 6. Modules and Functions of the Training Programs Authoring Tool

Module	Function
Training Content Gateway	Upload and select resources
XR Material Authoring Toolkit	Convert content to XR materials

XR Content Generator	Automate XR content creation
XR Training Materials Manager	Organize and interconnect XR materials
XR Training Programs Manager	Assemble and manage training programs
XR Training API	Integrate external access

Training Content Gateway

This module works as the main entry point for uploading or selecting training resources. Managers can upload traditional training files like PDFs, images, and videos, or choose from previously stored assets. The interface of the Training Content Gateway is provided through a user-friendly web interface and integrates with the XR Training Asset Repository for accessing the digital assets (Figure 15).

Figure 15 - Training content gateway interface

XR Material Authoring Toolkit

After uploading the content, the Authoring Toolkit enables managers to convert traditional resources into interactive XR formats. This includes extracting text or images from PDFs, linking videos with annotations, or setting up procedural instructions. This tool also supports 3D models through the 3D Model importer (Figure 16) for generating exploded views and workflow builder (currently under development).

Figure 16 - 3D Model Importer

XR Content Generator

This system is currently under development and aims to automate parts of the content conversion process. The XR Content Generator analyses the existing materials and generates XR-ready items such as interactive workflows or checklists from PDF files. This system also complements and provides an automated alternative to the semi-automated tool for content extraction from the XR Material Authoring Toolkit. This automation will simplify repetitive tasks and allows a streamline process of generating XR based materials.

XR Training Materials Manager

After being converted or generated, training items are stored and organized in this module. Managers can update, and link different materials to create a training program using XR-based materials such as checklists, videos, and interactive images materials created from the traditional training materials. This interconnected approach helps create a training program relying on a simple, structured, and scalable structure. A screenshot describing the user interface is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17 - Screenshot of the user interface for the XR Training Materials Manager

XR Training Programs Manager

In this stage of preparation of the training program, managers can assemble materials into structured training programs. Each program includes goals, objectives, and the specific XR materials to be rendered in the XR visualization. The module helps sequence the materials so trainees can progress through tasks or lessons in each training program. Through this module, managers can also associate quizzes or evaluation tools to be used as materials in the learning flow. These materials can be associated with a training program to assess knowledge and skills acquired after completing the program (Figure 18).

Figure 18 - Screenshot of the user interface for the XR Training Programs Manager

5.2. XR Training Plugin (XRTP)

The XRTP integrates several modules that interact to present XR training content. These modules comprise features related to the visualization of immersive training materials in XR environments, encompassing data retrieval and conversion to content organization and interactive display allowing users to effectively engage with XR training programs to achieve improved learning outcomes. The diagram with the interaction between the modules of the XRTP is presented below (Figure 19).

Figure 19 - Diagram illustrating the interaction between modules of the XRTP

Core Features and Functionalities

At a functional level, the XRTP is divided into different modules for providing the XR training materials and programs (Table 7).

Table 7. Modules and Functions of the XR Training Plugin

Module	Function
Training Programs Manager	Organizes and administers XR training programs and their content.
Training Data Service	Retrieves and communicates training data with the training platform.
Training Interface Toolkit	Provides immersive, user-friendly interfaces for content display.
Virtual Dashboard System	Manages and arranges multiple real-time views in the XR environment.
Adaptive Interface Engine	Dynamically adjusts interface elements based on user interactions.

Training Program Manager

This module works as the central coordinator of the visualization tool for structuring and rendering the retrieved programs. It allows operators to select specific training sessions, view program details, and launch materials, ensuring a coherent learning experience.

Training Data Service

This module is used for retrieving XR training programs and materials from the XR training repository (please see D5.3 for a detailed description of the XR Asset Repository), ensuring that trainees and operators have access to the most recent training content updated by the managers.

Training Interface Toolkit

This module converts the raw training data into immersive materials. The XR-based materials created or generated from the training materials are reviewed and updated in the TPAT and are rendered by the visualization tool using this module. It displays checklists, videos, workflows, or other content in user-friendly formats, enabling smooth interaction and navigation within XR environments.

Virtual Dashboard System

Providing a centralized workspace, the Virtual Dashboard System, currently being developed, organizes all active views and training modules. Operators can customize the dashboard by docking or undocking windows to prioritize critical information and maintain a clear overview. For instance, an operator may choose to dock a workflow viewer alongside a video player during a maintenance training session, allowing to simultaneously follow procedural steps and view real-time instructions.

Adaptive Interface Engine

This module is also being developed for the XR5.0 project. It will allow tracking of user behavior during the performance of the training programs, tailoring the interface to individual needs. It can rearrange content or highlight crucial steps, ensuring an efficient and personalized training environment. For example, in XR training for a given operator who is learning to perform a complex maintenance procedure on industrial equipment. As the operator interacts with the training program, the Adaptive Interface Engine monitors implicit metrics such as gaze patterns, executive times, and interaction frequency. If the system detects that the operator reveals difficulty on a particular step, it can automatically adjust the interface to support that step by enlarging the relevant controls providing additional visual cues or simplified instructions. On the other hand, if the operator completes other sections easily, the interface may reduce non-essential elements, allowing the operator to focus on the more challenging tasks. This dynamic adjustment reduces cognitive load and enhances learning by guiding the operator through the procedure in real time.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS TOWARDS VERSION 2

This deliverable aimed to establish a comprehensive foundation for the XR Training Management System within the XR5.0 Training Platform. This deliverable detailed the process of gathering and documenting the training materials, which allowed the selection of the most important materials to be used by the training platform and to be converted to XR-based materials. The document also described the design, development, and integration of two core components: the TPAT and the XRTP. These tools support managers to use training content, such as PDFs, images, videos, and 3D models, into immersive XR content, and to group these resources into structured XR training programs. This system aims to promote scalability for different contexts of efficient, user-friendly, and immersive training programs to ensure that both content creation and visualization are aligned with the evolving industrial training needs under the Industry 5.0 paradigm.

As for the next steps towards the second version of this deliverable, several pivotal steps will contribute to the evolution of the XR Training Management System and the method to adapt and display the XR-based materials and programs. It is planned to implement an automated tool for content extraction and generation, which will facilitate the process of converting traditional materials to XR materials. As work progresses, the 3D Model Explorer will also be introduced, enhancing the interactivity and visual understanding of 3D training content. In addition, pilot content from traditional materials used in each pilot context will also be implemented to showcase the creation of XR Training Materials, demonstrating the practical application of our mapping procedure in real-world scenarios. The analysis of both the opportunities and limitations of the mapping approach presented in this deliverable sets the ground for a comprehensive framework that will inform the ongoing development of the training platform's components.

Further integration efforts will focus on connecting the XR Training Plugin with the broader XR Training Platform, ensuring that all components operate in orchestration. The evaluation method for training programs will also be implemented to measure the effectiveness and impact of the immersive learning experiences. These tools will be used as XR-based materials to aim at evaluating the program using questionnaires and other methods for accessing skills and knowledge retention. These upcoming steps will contribute to the validation of the current functionality and to the continuous improvement of the XR5.0 Training Platform

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